

THE TERNARY SYSTEM. AMMONIUM NITRATE-AMMONIUM SULPHATE-WATER AT 25°.

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In the system NH_4NO_3 - $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - H_2O studied at 25°, two double salts $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{SO}_4 \cdot 3\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ are formed respectively. No salt hydrate is formed.

The system NH_4NO_3 - $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - H_2O was studied by Massink (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 351). It has been reinvestigated at 25° as a part of the work entailed in the study of the quaternary system, H_2O - K_2SO_4 - KNO_3 - $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - NH_4NO_3 at 25°, still under investigation. The vapour phase has been assumed to be absent and the whole subject has been treated as a condensed system at atmospheric pressure.

The method adopted for the study of the various complexes of ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulphate stirred up to equilibrium at 25° was the same as in the ternary system, potassium nitrate-ammonium nitrate-water at 25° (Bahl and Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 441).

The ammonium was determined by the usual distillation method and the nitrate was estimated by Lunge's nitrometer as given by Scott ("Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1925, Vol. I, p. 353). The amounts of sulphate and water were calculated by difference. These values were also checked by estimating sulphate as barium sulphate.

Fig. 1.

The system at 25° is complicated by the existence of two double salts, the compositions of which have been found to be $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4, 3\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4, 2\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ respectively. It is shown in Fig. 1 and the data for composition by weight for this system at the above temperature are given below.

Solution.			Rest.		Solid phases.
NH_4NO_3 .	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.	NH_4NO_3 .	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.		
68'27%	0 %	...	...		NH_4NO_3
65'43	2'25	75'50	1'88		NH_4NO_3
64'10	3'95	72'10	17'62		NH_4NO_3 D ₂
62'50	4'56	63'10	20'95		NH_4NO_3 D ₂
59'54	6'24	61'91	18'75		D ₂
57'62	7'51	60'01	35'61		D ₂ D ₁
55'78	8'46	54'88	27'43		D ₁
51'41	10'83	53'00	27'72		D ₁
47'95	13'58	40'51	48'11		D ₁ $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
45'47	14'92	25'10	53'23		$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
32'14	22'21	15'47	62'51		$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
15'21	32'97	5'26	77'12		$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
...	43'43	...	...		$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$

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